

EVALUATION OF WIND ENERGY FOR POWER GENERATION IN BAUCHI STATE NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study evaluated the wind power potential of a selected site (Bauchi) in Nigeria using wind speed data from 2015 to 2020, which were analyzed by Weibull probability distribution function. The average annual wind speed variation of the site lies between 2.05 m/s and 2.13 m/s. The shape factor K lies between 8.619 and 6.043, while the scale factor c lies between 7.33 m/s and 4.10 m/s. The average wind speed range of 2.05m/s-2.13m/s is small but sufficient enough for small scale wind turbines with cut-in speeds of 2.0m/s hence, the site can be used for water pumping and battery charging. Selection of wind turbine was basically done on the average wind speed on the study site which has to be sufficient to meet the cut-in wind speed. Tumo-Int 400W wind turbine generator is suitable for the study site; it is efficient even at lower wind speed. It is recommended that more sites should be studied, as wind is stochastic in nature so as to get more accurate and comprehensive wind profile for Nigeria. The government also needs to develop good policy that would foster the development of wind energy technology and attract investors.

Keywords: Wind speed, Weibull, Tumo-Int 400W wind turbine, energy.

INTRODUCTION

Provision and supply of energy to consumers has become erratic over the years coupled with the fact that emission from power stations powered by conventional fuel sources pose environmental concerns leads to climate change which is worrisome. Adopting renewable energy resources for energy needs has become a notable objective globally (EIA, (2020). Most countries of the world have since begun the process of harnessing and developing other alternative sources of energy. Moreover, the vast majority of these resources

are abundant, free and eco-friendly. In the early years wind has been used to sail the seas, grind grain, saw timber, press oil, shred tobacco, and pump water. The wind swept lowlands Zaan estuary of the Netherlands was a forerunner of the industrial revolution, during which windmills were mechanically powering machines (Okedu et al. 2015)

Nigeria, Africa's most populous country, faces unique challenges in its energy sector. Despite its abundant natural resources, including significant wind energy potential which is significant in addressing its energy shortfall,

promoting sustainable development, providing electricity to remote areas, and contributing to economic growth by leveraging clean, abundant, and inexhaustible wind resources, Nigeria struggles with severe energy deficits. The country's energy infrastructure is inadequate, leading to frequent power outages and a reliance on fossil fuels, particularly oil and gas, for electricity generation (Ohunakin 2010, Oyedepo 2015 and Aji et al. 2015).

The energy problem and the necessity for a renewable energy mix were explored by (Olaoye et al.2016), they stated that while Nigeria is rich in oil and natural resources, the country has never had an adequate supply of electricity throughout its history of electricity generating. This situation may deteriorate as the country's population grows and economic development necessitates more energy demand. They also noted that fossil fuels are gradually depleting, and that in order to rescue the environment from global warming, countries are turning to alternate energy sources to suit their needs. It was therefore critical that renewable energy solutions be supplied to meet Nigeria's looming industrialization and its ensuing energy crisis, which has left many enterprises operating at a loss and countless private houses without power.

Many studies were carried out on wind resource assessment around the world to

determine the potentialities of local sites for wind power/electricity generation (Xi, et al 2009, Chipo and Patrick, 2015, Goh et al 2016, Baloch, et al 2017), Also, several studies on wind resource assessment have been done in Nigeria (Samuel, and Muhammad, 2017). Each of these reports considered different sites and present analyses justifying their results (Abdulkarim et al.2017, Ohakwere-Eze et al 2020. Ignatius et al 2021. Samuel, et al 2023, Samuel, et al 2024). Energy Commission of Nigeria Development Programme (Sambo, 2009), reported that due to the varying topography and roughness of the nation, large differences in distribution within the same localities exist. This is corroborated by the fact that wind resources are site specific.

A site-by-site assessment is therefore necessary in order to come up with a comprehensive summary of the wind potential data for the country, which will technically aid in proper wind classification for the nation (Shehu, 2017). Hence, the main focus of this study is on the evaluation of wind profile for Bauchi in the Northern part of the Nigeria.

Materials and Method

Materials used for the analysis of wind profile for the study were;

- (i) Daily wind speed data for Bauchi, was collected from NiMet for the year 2015 to 2020.
- (ii) Microsoft Excel:

Method

Data Analysis

To define wind speed frequency distributions and classify the wind profile characteristics of a place, many statistical probability density functions have been applied. The methods range from normal parametric distributions to distributions based on the maximum entropy principle. The gamma distribution function, normal and lognormal distributions, Rayleigh, Weibull, and other statistical distributions have all been used recently (Adeyeye, et al 2020). The 2-parameter Weibull distribution, however, is the most widely used statistical probability density function (Power Generation, 2019). This was due to the fact that some of the other distributions did not fit the observed data well. More importantly, even when others provide a superior fit (e.g., the nonparametric kernel density function), they cannot be utilized to estimate the two crucial parameters for wind farm appraisal, the form factor and the scale factor, or to conduct additional technical analysis. The Weibull results likewise have the highest statistical significance (Manwell et al 2009 and Power

Generation 2019). As a result, the 2-parameter Weibull distribution has proven to be quite adaptable for determining a place's wind profile (Manwell et al 2009). It is still considered the greatest in terms of quality and application variety. As a result, the approach was used in this investigation.

The wind data analysis was carried out on the wind speed data acquired from NiMet using the 2-parameter Weibull distribution to define the wind speed frequency distribution and to classify the wind profile characteristics of the selected sites. This is the most widely used statistical probability density function (Adeyeye, et al, 2020).

Weibull 2-Parameter Model Function of Probability Density

The wind profile of the study site was evaluated using following equations

- i. **Probability density function:** The Weibull probability density function is given as expressed in equation 1; Power Generation, (2019).

$$f(v) = \left(\frac{k}{c}\right) \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^{k-1} \exp \left[-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k \right] \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Where;

$f(v)$ = Weibull distribution function

c = Weibull scale parameter in m/s

k = Weibull shape parameter

v = wind speed in m/s

ii. Cumulative probability function: The cumulative probability function of the Weibull distribution is given as (Manwell et al 2009)

$$F_w = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^k \right] \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Where;

F_w = Weibull cumulative distribution function

iii. Mean wind speed: The mean wind speed is given as

$$V_m = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where;

V_m = mean wind in m/s

iv. Standard deviation: The standard deviation was evaluated by (Manwell et al 2009).

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (V_i - V_m)^2} \dots \dots \dots 4$$

Where;

σ = the standard deviation

v. Weibull shape factor: The Weibull shape factor is given by

$$k = \left[\frac{\sigma}{V_m} \right]^{-1.086} \dots \dots \dots 5$$

Where;

k = Weibull shape factor

vi. Weibull scale factor: The Weibull scale factor is given by (Manwell et al 2009).

$$c = \frac{V_m}{\Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{k} \right)} \dots \dots \dots 6$$

Where;

$\Gamma(x)$ = the gamma function of x

vii. Wind power density: The wind power density is of two types which are given as (Manwell et al 2009). The first one is based on the available wind power as measured by the conversion system and computed directly from wind speed.

$$P(v) = \frac{1}{2} \rho A V^3 \dots \dots \dots 7$$

The second one is based on the Weibull 2-parameter method.

$$p(v) = \frac{1}{2} \rho c^3 \left(1 + \frac{3}{k} \right) \dots \dots \dots 8$$

Where;

$P(v)$ = wind power in Watts

$p(v)$ = wind power density in

W/m²

ρ = density of air in the site in

kg/m³

A = swept area

viii. Wind energy potential: The potential of wind energy is the available energy per unit area perpendicular to the wind stream during a particular period of time and is expressed by kinetic energy (Manwell et al 2009) which is given as

$$E_a = 0.5 \rho V^3 \dots \dots \dots 9$$

Where;

E_a = theoretical total energy available to system operating at its highest efficiency which operate the turbine

Note that only a small portion of the total energy would be retrieved $E_m = 0.2965\rho V^3 \dots \dots \dots 10$

A coefficient of performance known as the Beltz limit ($16/27 \approx 0.593$), limits the maximum extractable energy from a given energy

Where;

E_m = maximum extractable

Note that this makes the extractable energy approximately 59.3% of the theoretical energy.

3.0 Results and Discussion.

The daily wind speed for the period of six years (2015-2020) were assessed from the

Nigeria Meteorological Agency Abuja and subjected to Weibull two parameter distribution probability function analyses

Average wind speed:

annual average values and the results were presented

The daily mean wind speed data for the study site considered in this work were averaged into on the Figures below;

Table 1; Annual average wind speed data for Bauchi in m/s

Year				2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Bauchi	2.11	2.05	2.06	2.11	2.07	2.13			

Figure 1: Annual average shape factor against period

Figure 2: Annual average scale factor against period

Figure 3: Annual average Power Density against period

Figure 4: Annual average Theoretical Energy against period

Figure 5: Annual average Extractable Energy against period

4.0. Discussion

The daily wind speed for the period of six years (2015-2020) were assessed from the Nigeria Meteorological Agency Abuja and subjected to Weibull two parameter distribution probability function analyses. The annual average wind speed for the period considered is presented on Table 1, indicating low wind potential which is promising for small-scale or low cut-in speed wind turbines.

The Weibull shape parameter (k) result presented on Figure 1 is higher which indicate a very narrow distribution suggesting that the wind speeds are highly consistent and close to the mean value.

The Weibull scale factor (c) as observed from Figure 2 is low, increased with respect to

increase in wind speed for the range of period considered which indicated that the potentiality of the wind power of the site is directly proportional to the wind speed.

The average values for the period considered were as follows, wind speed was 2.0883 m/s, Standard deviation 0.0325 m/s, Shape factor 91.92, Scale factor 2.102 m/s, power density 5.512 W/m² theoretical energy 48.285 kWh/ m² and extractable energy 36.21 kWh/ m².

Selection of wind turbine was basically done on the average wind speed on the study site which has to be sufficient to meet the cut-in wind speed. From the results of the analysis in Figure.1., it could be deduced that based on the cut-in speed, wind turbine specification for the study site is Tumo-Int 400W wind turbine generator, with cut-in wind speed of 2 m/s,

efficient even at lower wind speed, making it ideal for areas with variables wind conditions like Bauchi.

5.0. Conclusion and Recommendations

The average annual minimum wind speed for study site is below 3.0 m/s. Bauchi tend to be a low site for the harvest of wind energy indicated by its low profile and can be used for residential application (small-scale), water pumping for irrigation, wind-powered water pumping systems, lighting, charging, electric livestock fencing, wind-powered drying of crops, telecommunication towers etc.

6.0. Recommendations

- (i) More sites should be studied, as wind is stochastic in nature so as to get more accurate and comprehensive wind profile for Nigeria.
- (ii) Further studies on the design of wind turbine should be done using the present analysis.
- (iii) The government also needs to develop good policy that would foster the development of wind energy technology, attract investors both foreign and domestic and also set standards for wind farm development.

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